

Love in the Time of Corona

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I just wanted the title to rhyme with the Marqueesian masterpiece. A more apt title would be “God, the Unconditional Love, and meaning of human suffering in the time of Corona pandemic and Global recession.” As of now, 1.2 million people are infected by the pandemic globally. The logarithmic graph on the web page of ‘worldometer’ shows no sign of its decline. In one month’s time, the virus can reach ten-fold. We do not know how and when the pandemic is going to end. Many countries are under a total or partial shutdown. IMF has made a prediction that the virus’ fall-out will lead to a financial meltdown ‘way worse’ than the global financial crisis a decade ago. Humankind is facing an unprecedented global crisis.

”Why does God allow suffering?” would be ‘the question’ that disturbs the minds of believers and skeptics alike at this moment. This ‘problem of evil’ is originally attributed to the Greek philosopher Epicurus. If God is omnipotent and merciful, how can there be evil!!! We can blame humans for moral evils like rape, murder and theft. But whom can we blame for physical evils like

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earthquake, flood and pandemic? Epicurus may stand up from his grave and scream at the faithful for vindicating God at the face of suffering. The truth is that there is no convincing answer to the problem of evil. We simply do not know. We come to this deadlock because we take the wrong approach.

Natural Calamities as Part of Nature

As Steven Pinker (2019) says in *Enlightenment Now*, “the first step towards wisdom is the realization that the laws of the universe do not care for us.” But God does! Volcanic eruptions, flood and epidemics are natural events or occurrences. These calamities had been happening on planet earth even before we humans were born 3.5 million years ago. There was a time when the planet earth was a volcanic furnace. Tectonic plate movements carved the continents. Seismic activities will continue to shake the earth as long as it exists. Viruses appeared on the planet 1500 million years ago. They are among the oldest ancestors of life. As depicted in *Guns, Germs and Steel* by Jared Diamond (2008), the Eurasians were prone to Virus attacks from animals for a very long time. Slowly they gained immunity to many of the viruses and acquired an upper hand over some other human races which were not as immune to the viruses as the Eurasians. Still, there are a great number of viruses in animals which are constantly undergoing mutations. “It is figuring us out faster than we are figuring it out. It doesn’t have anything else to do.” These prophetic words from the film *Contagion* (2011) is very much true in its case (Cook 2014). So far, we have not developed a reliable method to overcome the threat from many varieties of viruses. Since we have a written and well-recorded history of only a few thousand years, we do not have much idea about the extreme struggles our ancestors have had gone through over millions of years. Natural calamities have happened in the past and it will happen in the future too. We should be ready and willing to face them irrespective of whether we are believers or not.

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Hope in God

Darwinian theory of evolution argues that Nature selects and promotes the fittest. However, fitness is often misrepresented as mere muscle power. Evolutionary biology reveals that the species which survived a crisis was not the strongest among the rest but the one which was ready to constantly adapt and endure. Neanderthals were more powerful and numerous than us, *Homo sapiens*. But it was us who survived and not them. Despite of physical disadvantages, we were better at survival than them because of our extraordinary ability at socializing. It helps us to realize that extreme suffering does not imply that life is meaningless because there are people who care for us. Anyone with a humanistic sensibility cares about you in the sense of realizing that we all have a responsibility “to use the laws of universe to enhance the conditions in which all of us can flourish” (Pinker 2019). Standing together at the time of calamities gives great strength. Today we see most of the human population respecting government mandates; and medical staff and public workers toil day and night to care for the sick and to stop the outbreak. As the German philosopher, Friedrich Nietzsche said: “What doesn't kill you makes you stronger”. In the coming years, climate change will release more of these demons from the underground. The present crisis is an excellent opportunity to prepare for the future. For the first time in the history of life on planet earth, a species has attained the capability to nourish or destroy the chain of life. We have a choice. It is all up to us. As St Ignatius of Loyola said, “Act as if everything depended on you; trust as if everything depended on God.”

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The naturalistic and rationalistic approach alone will not help us to endure extreme sufferings and losses. We will soon succumb to despair or angst – life lacks meaning – in the language of Soren Kierkegaard. This is where we cannot proceed without God. Faith, Hope and Love are called Divine Virtues. For a long time in my early youth, I struggled to understand the relevance of Hope. “Faith and Love are enough, why do we need Hope?” I thought. Life has taught me how important hope is. For a person who believes only in the materialistic reality, life is not worth in the midst of extreme and unstoppable suffering. Hope helps a person to see the light beyond the darkness. Even if there is no mathematical probability for the end of struggles, Hope will help one to endure. The Israelites were one among the many tribes of the ancient’s times, insignificant and weak in front of the domineering Egyptians, the Persians and many others. The powerful Pharaonic and Babylonian races had gone down in history but, Israel still endures and makes a significant impact on the world. Hope helps us to sing like the prophet Habakkuk : “Though the fig tree does not bud and there are no grapes on the vines, though the olive crop fails and the fields produce no food, though there are no sheep in the pen and no cattle in the stalls, yet I will rejoice in the Lord, I will be joyful in God my Savior. The Sovereign Lord is my strength; he makes my feet like the feet of a deer; he enables me to tread on the heights” (Hab 3:17).

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Never Surrender

This crisis is also a time to be grateful. Scientists of 40 international research institutes are working round the clock to develop a vaccine for this disease. The often forgotten scientific community gave us vaccinations for small pox, polio and many dreadful diseases. It is

estimated that over the years more than 5 billion lives are saved due to the effort of around 100 scientists (and their teams). It is time to remember all of them with a grateful heart. God is not some one who is very remote from us. He labours for us and with us through the scientists, police personals and politicians as said by St. Ignatius in his “Contemplation to attain Love.”

We shall fight this crisis with the will of Winston Churchill: “We shall defend human life, whatever the cost may be, we shall fight in the research labs, we shall fight in the hospitals, we shall fight in the fields and in the streets, we shall fight by isolating ourselves; we shall never surrender.”

We shall never surrender to natural calamities. We must fight and endure with Faith, Hope and Love.

God is with us. Love, Ultimate, Unconditional Love, will triumph!

References

- Pinker, S. (2019). *Enlightenment Now*. New York: Penguin Books Ltd.
Diamond, Jared. (2008). *Guns, Germs, and Steel: The Fates of Human Societies*. Paw Prints.
Cook, R. (2014). *Contagion*. London: Bello.

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